

LITERARY PSYCHOLOGIZM AS A REFLECTION OF HUMAN'S INTERNAL WORLD

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Annotation: *This article is about the main aspect of the literary work the literary psychologism. Psychologism, is a stylistic unity, a system of means and techniques aimed at a complete, deep and detailed disclosure of the inner world of the characters. Psychologism as the ability to penetrate into the inner world of a person is inherent in any art to one degree or another. However, it is literature that has unique opportunities to master mental states and processes due to the nature of its imagery.*

Key words: *Literary psychologism, character, protagonist, literary heroine, deep feelings, fiction*

The literary hero has always been one of the most important problems of literature. The depiction of man and the world is first and foremost reflected in the literary heroes. Through the symbols of the heroes, the reader understands the writer's attitude to life problems, to the human person, to conflicting events. Writers, depicting the spiritual life of the hero, tend to turn to his deep feelings - to show him in great grief, in joy. Their goal is to cause sincere sympathy for their hero.

There the main role places the psychological characteristics of the author. The problem of psychologism in modern fiction incurrantly underdeveloped and understudied. It should be noted that artistic psychologism has not yet been fully defined as a subject of scientific study. In a literary work, psychologism is a set of means used to display the internal hero's world: for a detailed analysis of his thoughts, feelings and experiences. Psychologism in literature is a description of the hero's inner world by artistic means. There is a whole discussion about terminological definition of psychologism. The Russian scholar A. B. Yesin discussed this problem: “psychologism is a fairly complete, detailed and deep depiction of feelings, thoughts, and experiences of a fictional personality (literary character) with the help of specific means of literature”.¹ For the author, there are no secrets in the soul of the hero - he knows everything about him, can trace in detail the internal processes, explain the causal relationship between impressions, thoughts, experiences. The narrator can comment on the hero's introspection, talk about those spiritual movements that the hero himself cannot notice or that he does not want to admit to himself.

¹ Yesin, A. B. Psychologism of Russian classical literature: A book for teachers / A. B. Esin. - M.: Enlightenment, 1988. -P.18

The first attempts to substantiate the forms of psychologism are presented in the studies of M.V. Khrapchenko, who delivered a dynamic, logical and analytical principles of depiction of characters, directly related to calling them with the typology of the psychological image. There are attempts build a typology of psychological image forms, taking into account the system we are narrative-compositional forms with different artistic possibilities in terms of depicting the inner world heroes. The concept of the typology of psychologism, developed taking into account whether directly or through external symptoms are transmitted to the inner world of the character, and supported most domestic literary critics (I. V. Strakhov, L. Ya. Ginzburg, V. E. Khalizev, A. I. Andreev).

One of the techniques of psychologism is an artistic detail. External details (portrait, landscape, world of things) have long been used for the psychological depiction of mental states in the system of an indirect form of psychologism. Thus, portrait details (for example, “turned pale”, “blushed”, “hung his head wildly”, etc.) conveyed the psychological state “directly”; at the same time, of course, it was implied that one or another portrait detail was unambiguously correlated with one or another spiritual movement. The portrait characteristic in the system of psychologism is enriched by the author's commentary, clarifying epithets, psychologically deciphered, and sometimes, on the contrary, encrypted so that the reader himself takes the trouble to interpret this mimic or gesture movement. The details of the landscape also very often have a psychological meaning. Certain states of nature in one way or another correlate with certain human feelings and experiences (psychological parallelism).² However, the internal state character can either correspond to the natural, or contrast with him.

Another technique of psychologism is the description of the situation surrounding the hero. The internal psychological point of view assumes that the subject and the object of psychological observation are merged, which corresponds to structure of the first person narrative. Techniques inherent in this positions: confession, diary entries, internal monologue (without traces the presence of the narrator), "stream of consciousness".³ The "stream of consciousness" technique is traditionally perceived as a form of internal monologue taken to its limit. Such understanding is connected with the idea of consciousness as a river with many currents (thoughts, associations, sensations, memory images), synchronously coexisting (in the interpretation of J. James)⁴.

Determining the place of psychologism in the general system of literary concepts and categories, it should first be noted that, since psychologism is an image of the inner world of characters, and the images of characters, in turn, in

² Yesin, A. B. Psychologism of Russian classical literature: A book for teachers / A. B. Esin. - M.: Enlightenment, 1988. —P.79-80

³ Yesin, A. B. Psychologism of Russian classical literature: A book for teachers / A. B. Esin. - M.: Enlightenment, 1988. —P.94

⁴ Zolotukhina, O.B. Psychologism in the literature: a special course manual / O.B. Zolotukhina. - Grodno: GRGU, 2009. - P.45.

literary criticism it is customary to refer to such a side of the art form as subject representation.

Thus, psychologism is a special technique, a form that allows you to correctly and vividly depict mental movements. There are three main forms of psychological representation: direct, indirect and summative. Psychologism has its own internal structure, that is, it consists of techniques and methods of representation, the most common of which are internal monologue and psychological author's narration. In addition to them, there is the use of dreams and visions, double heroes and the technique of default.

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